

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND TECHNO-BANKING EDUCATION: IMPACTS ON THE TEACHING-LEARNING PROCESS¹

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to analyze how technological change alters productive and educational processes. The text points out that, despite the appeal of modernization and innovation, the spread of artificial intelligence technologies alters the relationship between language and thought, producing a technobanking education whose effects generate submission, domination, exploitation, and universalization of a single way of thinking. The article starts from Marx's analyses of machinery and develops by pointing out changes, contradictions, and challenges on the subject. Finally, ways to address the issue are presented in order to generate an education committed to the interests of emancipation of the dominated class.

Keywords: Technobanking education; Artificial Intelligence; Education.

INTELIGÊNCIA ARTIFICIAL E EDUCAÇÃO TECNOBANCÁRIA: IMPACTOS NO PROCESSO ENSINO-APRENDIZAGEM

Resumo

O objetivo deste estudo é analisar como a mudança tecnológica altera processos produtivos e educativos. O texto aponta que, apesar do apelo de modernização e inovação, a difusão de tecnologias de inteligência artificial altera a relação entre linguagem e pensamento, produzindo uma educação tecnobancária cujos efeitos geram submissão, dominação, exploração e universalização de um pensamento único. O artigo parte das análises de Marx sobre a maquinaria e se desenvolve apontando alterações, contradições e desafios sobre o tema. Ao final, são apresentados caminhos para o enfrentamento da questão no sentido de gerar uma educação comprometida com os interesses de emancipação da classe dominada.

Palavras-chave: Educação tecnobancária; Inteligência Artificial; Educação.

INTELIGENCIA ARTIFICIAL Y EDUCACIÓN TECNOBANCARIA: IMPACTOS EN EL PROCESO DE ENSEÑANZA-APRENDIZAJE

Resumen

El objetivo de este estudio es analizar cómo el cambio tecnológico cambia los procesos productivos y educativos. El texto señala que, a pesar del atractivo de la modernización y la innovación, la difusión de tecnologías de inteligencia artificial cambia la relación entre lenguaje y pensamiento, produciendo una educación tecnobancaria cuyos efectos generan sumisión, dominación, exploración y universalización de un solo pensamiento. El artículo parte del análisis de Marx sobre la maquinaria y se desarrolla señalando cambios, contradicciones y desafíos en el tema. Al final, se presentan formas de afrontar el tema para generar una educación comprometida con los intereses de emancipación de la clase dominada.

Palabras clave: Educación tecnobancaria; Inteligencia artificial; Educación.

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Introduction

The advance of capital, especially in the neoliberal period of structural crisis, has led to the imposition of new means and strategies of adaptation. In this context, various movements are identified as strategies to expand the exploitation of labor and human knowledge. In the case of education, new models are presented and implemented as requirements for the modernization of processes, methods, and resources that are necessary and urgent. However, what we observe is that such strategies, in reality, reveal themselves to be reactionary and conservative, regressing and attacking rights, confiscating knowledge, and contributing to the dehumanization of men and women.

The work is divided into three main parts: the first will present discussions on the advancement of machinery, pointing to the consequences in the productive sphere in terms of changing work, increasing its intensity, precariousness, and control. The second part attempts to relate technological transformation and innovation to the educational context, identifying movements and effects of this movement more broadly. In the third and final section, a reflection is developed on digital resources, artificial intelligence, and new technologies in the teaching-learning process. The conclusion of the study will allow us to recognize changes in the relationship between language and thought in the sense of spreading a technobanking model of education, with a view to implementing a human education centered on a single way of thinking.

Historical and dialectical materialism serves as the theoretical and methodological basis for this work. The research consists of a dialectical analysis of reality, the results of which tend to materialize in theories and categories that will return to reality in order to generate knowledge and resistance in the face of attacks. All analysis is done with a view to pointing out contradictions and limits in the use of technologies as they are currently used, whose effects are masked in order to make the advance of the movement in question even more radical. Reflecting on this is necessary in order to become aware of the real situation, identifying strategies for capital action aimed at building paths of resistance.

The objective of the text is to understand how the development of technology alters not only productive processes but also educational processes within which strategies for the appropriation of knowledge, science, and technology aim at greater domination and exploitation of individuals, targeting the expansion of capitalist accumulation. In this sense, we identify how this movement, at the service of capital, approaches education and how technology, understood as a fetish, takes the place of humans, who become increasingly alienated and reified. Overcoming technobanking education through a human formation project that is emancipatory and liberating is the challenging, complex, necessary, and urgent path to transposing and reversing this situation.

Analysis of technology based on Marx's reflections on machinery

In his dense and careful analysis of the capitalist production process, Karl Marx (2017), in the first book of *Capital*, starts from the analysis of commodities, points to the production of value from labor, and highlights a series of concepts and categories that mark the development process of the capitalist mode of production. As a consequence of this study, the author deepens his thesis on the production of relative surplus value, from which he advances to the understanding of other concepts, namely: cooperation, division of labor, manufacturing, and industrial production. At this point, it is possible to analyze an important reflection on the phenomenon he calls machinery.

In the capitalist mode of production, machinery is responsible for "making goods cheaper" and shortening the part of the working day that the worker needs for himself, in order to prolong the other part of his working day, which he gives freely to the capitalist. Machinery is a means for the production of surplus value" (Marx, 2017, p. 445). However, when comparing the development of human labor with and without the support of technology and tools, the author states that: "in the tool, man would be the driving force, while the machine would be moved by a natural force different from the human one, such as that derived from animals, water, wind, etc." (Marx, 2017, p. 446). Thus, it can be observed that the use of a force other than human force already indicates a potential for production within the

capitalist mode, namely: its compatibility with the proposal for exponential and unlimited growth sought by capital.

This is why there is heavy investment in processes of continuous technological change, since the driving force of the machine can be seen as less imperfect, stronger, and less limited than that provided by humans. This indicates that, over time, there is an increasing search for the development of technologies emancipated from human labor, which can function independently, incessantly, and intermittently, unregulated by natural and ethical limits, based on the search for increased rates of accumulation.

Technology is transforming and adapting to the new demands of the process of exploiting surplus value and expropriating human labor, so that workers are becoming less and less necessary and more hidden within the process. Marx himself highlights the argument that supports this view when he states that "a single machine, assisted by an adult man or even a boy, prints as much four-color calico as two hundred men used to do" (Marx, 2017, p. 465). This brings about an important change in the entire process: a shift in the focus and foundation of the system. Whereas before it was the machine and technology that had to adapt to human labor, what we see today is an increasing need for workers to adapt to the new demands of the process.

At this point, it is crucial to mention one fact: despite all the apparent independence and autonomy of production and technological change in relation to human labor, we must not forget that machines and technology do not produce or operate on their own. From this, it can be inferred that capital still depends on human labor and knowledge in the process of value production: "like any other component of constant capital, machinery does not create any value, but transfers its own value to the product for whose production it serves" (Marx, 2017, p. 460).

This is the reason why capital continues to appropriate the knowledge produced by workers (through science, technology, and innovation) as a mechanism for capitalist accumulation. It is in this sense that Vera Cotrim (2009) states that the capital se appropriates the knowledge both to increase productivity

productivity as well as to transform knowledge into a vehicle for the production of surplus value. In both situations, what we observe is that knowledge of the work process—developed by and belonging to the worker—ends up being appropriated and assumed by capital via technological change. The consequence of this is the inclusion of appropriated knowledge in the reconstruction of the work process and ultimately passed on to workers with increased mechanisms of control, intensification, and exploitation.

We also agree with Sedi Hirano (2011), for whom, in the same way that capitalist accumulation expropriates not only means of labor or commodities, but also the knowledge of the working class. This occurs when the capitalist mode of production appropriates science through different modes and strategies. It is important to note that much of scientific research is carried out to satisfy capitalist interests, that is, many research topics are defined and funded for purposes clearly defined by capital. The production of scientific, technological, and innovative knowledge, rather than producing better living conditions, ends up contributing to capitalist accumulation by enabling the replacement of living labor with dead labor, increasing production and, consequently, relative surplus value.

The disposability of workers and the increase in the intensity and exploitation of labor are two strategies that go hand in hand with the advancement of machinery. Reflecting on the pioneering country of the Industrial Revolution, Marx is blunt in stating that "nowhere is there a more shameless waste of human strength for miserable occupations than in England, the country of machines" (Marx, 2017, p. 467). This should not be seen as a perverse effect or something that went wrong and got out of control. On the contrary: it is a fact that is part of the planned process and is even one of its objectives. By replacing living labor with machinery (dead labor), capital frees up a number of workers who will become unemployed and, as a result, forces those who remain employed to submit and accept all kinds of increases in working hours, intensification, and exploitation. This means that capital dictates the rules of work based on its interests of accumulation, remaining indifferent to the living conditions that these rules impose on the working class.

The need to accept increasingly intense work limits due to the excessive number of workers available to take the place of dissatisfied workers is a strategy used by capital to appease class struggle and undermine workers' demands. In a labor market regulated by the law of supply and demand, the greater the number of unemployed workers available, the lower the wages paid and the longer and more intense the working day. It is in this sense that machinery is understood to reduce human limits and barriers in order to extend, beyond natural limits, the working day, the intensity, and the productivity of labor. Even if society organizes itself to react to this movement, what we see is that capital will always circumvent this resistance by imposing new means of intensifying work within the limits set by ^{the} maximum working day.

Increased intensity and exploitation are possible within the capitalist mode of production because, with the advancement of machinery, conditions are created for increased control and surveillance of labor by capital. From this point on, the individual ceases to be the center and reference point from which the production process will take place, becoming just another cog in the wheel that now needs to work according to the time and control of the machine. It is as if the machine has become the subject and man the object, since it is the machine that dictates the entire order and intensity of movement in a factory. This situation is neither peaceful nor comfortable for the working class, since the intensification of work damages workers' health⁵. Increased exploitation, lower wages, higher unemployment, misery, and poverty are real products

⁴Marx shows in *Capital* that entrepreneurs have historically used many ways to get around labor laws on working hours and limits. The same book also highlights several situations where the courts sided with capital over the working class. The penalties and fines themselves (when rarely applied) were very small compared to the high profits that companies earned from breaking the law, showing that even this was good business. Currently, the real scenario is not far from that described by Marx: with the approval of the labor counter-reform, capital is radically advancing on labor in the sense of formalizing informal work, legalizing and deepening exploitation, destabilizing workers, allowing intermittent work, among a series of other measures

⁵ The first book of *Capital* provides a series of examples that present reports of successive accidents at work in different branches of production. In addition, indicators obtained from official reports and data on the decrease in life expectancy and recurring health problems among workers are also presented. Such problems and accidents are caused by the inhumane and degrading working conditions in the context of the expansion of the Industrial Revolution.

of the advance of the capitalist mode of production⁶. The alarming growth in the number of workplace accidents is also verified and explained by the fact that exhausted, tired, and untrained workers, with the advance of machinery, begin to use unsafe equipment.

What we see here is that, by taking the place of many workers, machinery increases competition among them, diminishing class cohesion and weakening any initiative for worker resistance. Competitiveness is based on the excessive exploitation of labor, since "the capacity for resistance of workers diminishes as a result of their dispersion" (Marx, 2017, p. 533). In addition, it is important to note that machinery is a way of blackmailing workers, especially during strikes. In this context of increased labor exploitation through the competitiveness generated by machinery, capital takes advantage of the situation to employ the entire family. Whereas before it was only men who worked (and needed to earn a wage capable of supporting the whole family), now all family members are thrown into the labor market (women and children), reducing the wage necessary for reproduction and appropriating both domestic work and the education of children. It is in this sense that parents will present themselves as having the right to put children to work, claiming that this will be a way of learning a trade and a path to personal growth and development. In fact, what we see here is an agenda that commodifies everything and, because of this, is compatible with the demands of capital. The capitalist mode of production leads parents to exploit their children, as it transforms everything into a commodity, into labor power for capitalist accumulation.

⁶ Reflecting on the general law of capitalist accumulation, Marx (2017), in *Capital*, shows that although many workers in England worked hard and continuously, they ended up starving. This indicates that, in a context of such misery, the situation of the working class was one of profound calamity, since when a person is already starving, they have lost all other conditions for living, such as housing, clothing, health, sanitation, heating, among others. The same degrading situation of the working class is described by Engels (2010), when he presents, in detail, the living, housing, and health conditions to which English factory workers were subjected.

Industry and school 4.0: impacts of the advance of capital and technological change on education

Capital not only alters production and family relationships, as pointed out in the previous section: it also alters and creates demands for education. Recapping a little of the history, it is possible to see that in Marx's context, large-scale industry needed to operate with fragmented, one-dimensional human beings who behaved like accessories to the machine. This is related to the need for the capitalist mode of production to transform complex work into simple work (Netto; Braz, 2012; Rubin, 1987). This reduction is directly related to the demand for worker training, because the more the work process is simplified, the lower the costs of training will be and, consequently, the lower the wages can be (Cotrim, 2009)⁷. It can be observed here that the need to simplify the complex work process prevails, with a view to disqualifying those who work, as developed by Marx in Capital:

In every trade it takes over, manufacturing thus creates a class of so-called unskilled workers, previously strictly excluded by craftsmanship. At the same time as it develops, at the expense of total working capacity, a totally one-sided specialization that reaches the point of virtuosity, it already begins to transform the absolute lack of development into a specialization. Along with hierarchical gradation, there is a simple separation between skilled and unskilled workers. For the latter, the costs of learning disappear completely, and for the former, these costs are lower than for artisans, due to the simplified function. In both cases, the value of the workforce decreases (MARX, 2017, p. 424).

The process of technological transformation and the consequent deepening of its forms of appropriation by capital produces a series of new realities and concepts. Schwab (2016) points out that the term Industry 4.0 was created in 2011 in order to relate technological changes to the fourth phase of the industrial revolution. The idea aims at the “automated digital awakening of dead labor, which as an autonomous force increasingly takes control over living labor.”

⁷ It is important to relate this point to the division that the capitalist mode of production operates between manual labor and intellectual labor, signaling the division between technical, scientific, and administrative workers and manual or manual laborers, imposing a division within the working class itself as a mechanism for weakening and diminishing class solidarity.

(Araújo, 2022, p. 23). Thus, a series of new concepts are emerging that are becoming increasingly recurrent in the world of work, such as automation, the Internet of Things (IoT), *machine* learning, the digital age, algorithms, artificial intelligence, robotics, among others.

All the changes in the 4.0 world will generate, as previously highlighted, the need for changes in the profile of workers required by the current mode of production, bringing demands and impacts to educational processes. Such situations trigger and inaugurate changes that reach schools in the form of what is known as education 4.0. It is possible to understand the relationship between schools and industry 4.0 when we observe that:

Education 4.0 emerges in the context of the so-called fourth industrial revolution and refers to its developments in the field of education, aiming to implement computer language, information technologies, robotization, artificial intelligence, and automation in the education system, with the goal of preparing the workforce to meet the needs of industry (SILVA; PEREIRA, 2021, p. 133).

At first glance, it is clear that Education 4.0 takes two specific and complementary forms within the school environment. The first form concerns innovations brought to the curriculum. Under the pretext of preparing individuals to be active, connected, versatile, and engaged with the technological changes of today's world, new knowledge and skills must be included in the school curriculum. Caetano and Porto Júnior (2021), in researching the topic, identified concepts and methods that are beginning to be part of the school discourse in order to guide changes in the curriculum, such as: *learning by doing*, *maker* culture, hybrid teaching, active methodologies, flipped classroom, new media, digital skills, entrepreneurship, social-emotional skills, innovation, and STEAM⁸.

The inclusion of these contents, methods, and proposals in the curriculum is based on the argument that technological advancement is a unique, necessary, urgent, and irreversible path: humanity has no alternative to education 4.0. The prevailing argument is that not adhering to this universe implies remaining behind and that any contrary discourse should be seen as obsolete. In addition, the appeal of

⁸ Acronym (*Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, Mathematics*) that signals the integration of these areas of knowledge in solving concrete problems.

⁹ It is important to note that this idea of modernization, as pointed out by Laval (2004), is not neutral. In this context, it is worth revisiting the idea of modernizing backwardness. To better

build the skills and abilities necessary for entry into a radically interactive, digital, and challenging job market also supports the proposal. However, this argument is immersed in a contradiction, since, in view of everything that has already been exposed, it is possible to see that this movement of technological restructuring has been implemented in order to transform living labor into dead labor, generating more and more unemployed individuals¹⁰.

Furthermore, it should also be noted that this discourse on education 4.0 produces a reconfiguration and limitation of the teaching function. In this context, teachers lose some of the depth of their role and become merely mediators and motivators of the process. Here, students learn on their own, autonomously, through active practices and methodologies. This is a simplification and reduction of education, which loses its theoretical, emancipatory, and human scope and becomes conceived solely as a means of adapting the workforce to the production system. Regarding these active and constructivist methodologies focused on "learning to learn" and "learning by doing," Newton Duarte (2011) states that the concept of meaningful learning ends up becoming an idea linked only to the interests and realities of students, based on an imminently pragmatic ideology, represented by a shallow, superficial, light educational project that does not bring any kind of expansion or broadening of the vision of learning, the needs and expectations of the teaching and learning process, nor the

To understand this, it is necessary to remember that in the Brazilian political, economic, and social context of the 1960s and 1970s, several sociologists devoted themselves to analyzing the contradictory transformations that took place in the country's development. Florestan Fernandes (1975) analyzed the process of national bourgeois revolution within a context of dependent capitalism. The author concluded that the nature of Brazil's conservative modernization process meant that this movement did not overcome the backwardness represented by the national elites (especially the agrarian elites), whose actions reinforced the country's dependence and subordination, seen only as a supplier of raw materials to the central countries. On the contrary, the Brazilian case used backwardness as an engine to drive modernization (FERNANDES, 2009). In the same vein, Francisco de Oliveira (2003) points out that, in Brazil, it was the archaic that leveraged the process of capitalist expansion and accumulation, producing, as a consequence, a small super-privileged class and a large mass of poor and destitute people. It cannot be denied, therefore, that the country's conservative modernization process was based on the marks of backwardness, among which authoritarianism, coronelismo, and the maintenance of exploitation, dependence, and inequality stand out.

¹⁰ It is worth noting that this argument is ultimately directly related to the issue of employability: a perverse discourse that transfers all responsibility for unemployment to the individual, denying the social and systemic causes that generate the lack of job opportunities. The strategy here is to mask the structural crisis in the world of work and attribute unemployment to individuals who do not have the skills and abilities demanded by the market.

search for a critical and liberating education. In this sense, the same author criticizes the rapprochement between education and the market:

The more the dissemination of knowledge is governed by market laws, the more superficial and immediate the knowledge offered to individuals becomes, and the more superficial and immediate the intellectual needs of these individuals become. We thus have a vicious circle in which the goal of immediate profit generates more widely and easily consumable products and, in turn, the needs and preferences of individuals become increasingly impoverished. In this context, defending "learning to learn" is to decree the defeat of knowledge and contribute to the process of emptying individuals, a process generated by the fact that exchange value is the universal mediation in capitalist society (DUARTE, 2011, p. 175–176).

This emptying of school education is not a mistake or an undesirable effect, but, as previously stated, part of the project. Conservative neoliberal practices need to rely on educational reforms with a view to spreading values and forming subjectivities aligned with the interests of capital. The formation of a subjectivity compatible with the market is developed by Dardot and Laval (2016) when they present the concept of the neoliberal subject, understood as the subject who exploits himself, using the company as a model for the realization of his life. In addition to further reifying and alienating the individual, this model aims to “manufacture useful men, docile to work, willing to consume, to manufacture the effective man” (Dardot; Laval, 2016, p. 325).

The second manifestation of Education 4.0 concerns the platformization of teaching, which is achieved through the use of digital and technological resources in the pedagogical process in order to consider education as a business opportunity for capital. There are several educational products offered by companies for education: platforms, applications, systems, classes, courses, programs, among others. In addition to generating the possibility of capitalist accumulation through the sale of these goods, these resources contribute to the logic of forming neoliberal subjectivities and increasingly limiting the role of teachers. Laval (2004) points to the fact that the sale of educational packages for teaching students and also for teacher training is a lucrative and expanding market. In order to function and expand, this market needs to undermine and devalue teacher training for two reasons:

to create teachers who are more dependent on technology and, at the same time, to attract customers (teachers) with fewer technical skills to evaluate the quality of the product/commodity they are consuming.

Furthermore, the aforementioned maxim of transforming living labor into dead labor remains here, through the appropriation of recorded classes that are sold to an incalculable and unlimited number of students who will have access to an education that, despite promoting interactivity and timeliness, will consist of a course based on formatted, asynchronous video lessons, without the possibility of debate or interactivity. It is in this context that Silva (2020) reflects on the phenomenon of the uberization and youtuberization of teaching. According to the author, uberization can be characterized as “total instability and absence of labor and social security rights” (Silva, 2020, p. 599), through the exemption of the employer of the courses from offering work, greater possibility of monitoring and controlling what is being done, and linking evaluation and accountability to the imposition of goals. In addition, youtuberization is understood as the moment when the teacher becomes a content producer who will be available on a platform for a very large number of students (most of whom are unknown to the teacher). This highlights a market and commercial relationship, within which each video lesson produced must be publicly evaluated by customers/users with a specific number of stars. The relationship between the two processes can be seen when we observe that:

If *uberization* breaks with the notion of public service and destroys it along with public teaching, during the pandemic, *youtuberization* affects education professionals and reshapes their relationship with the school in a process that increases the alienation and expropriation of teaching work (SILVA, 2020, p. 603).

It is important to highlight that, despite promising advances, modernization, and ease of access, this discourse of education 4.0 can become a path to further widening the educational inequality that is already a long-standing feature of our country. This is because we must not forget that the other side of technology is digital exclusion. This situation was laid bare during the pandemic, as students from low-income backgrounds or living in regions without stable connectivity had even greater difficulties in keeping up with their classes. Thus, it is still a challenge or even a contradiction to talk about digital and technological education

technology for students living in precarious conditions. This also applies to teachers, since not all of them have the training and digital literacy necessary to use these resources, which also leads to exclusion within the teaching profession. Silva (2020) calls this phenomenon "professorial Darwinism."

The Education 4.0 movement is being embraced, sponsored, and driven by influential sectors within the Federal Government. Nunes (2021), in analyzing the topic, identifies at least eight public notices from the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Science and Technology to encourage practices related to Education 4.0 in the country. In addition to the announcement of public notices, projects, and courses, it is interesting to note that this phenomenon is also gaining momentum in the discourse of educational management and evaluation. Freitas (2018), reflecting on the corporate reform of education, observes that instruments imported from private company management are being brought into education in order to generate competitiveness, increase individualism, and standardize processes. Imposed from the top down or stimulated by evaluation and accountability processes, these policies produce even more inequality, isolation, and precarious teaching conditions and encourage the formation of an increasingly alienated, commodified neoliberal subjectivity that is unable to organize resistance. Oliveira (2023) states that there is a privatization movement within the education sector in Brazil, producing non-public state institutions. This process is a consequence of neoliberal advances in three areas: management, evaluation, and financing tools; public-private partnerships; and the movement toward narrowing the curriculum.

Artificial Intelligence and technobanking education

The relationship between language, thought, and human development has already been highlighted in a series of works (Piaget, 1987; 1976; Vygotsky, 1991). With changes in technology, the internet, and, above all, artificial intelligence, what we see is that this relationship has been reconfigured. Ubal et al (2023) develop the theme by pointing to a change in the triad between student, knowledge, and teacher (Houssaye, 1988), highlighting that artificial intelligence resources and applications

– especially the use of Chat GPT – can take the place of the student, the teacher, or even knowledge itself.

The argument used here is based on the fact that the structure of the class (considered as a teaching and learning process) is language. Thus, with the use of language generated and produced by artificial intelligence, both teachers and students outsource their thinking to technology, renouncing the development of both. Here, we refer to the thinking of Ludwig Wittgenstein, an Austrian philosopher who states that “the limits of my language mean the limits of my world” (Wittgenstein, 2011, p. 245). In this sense, the change that artificial intelligence causes in the teaching triad disrupts and impairs the development of language and, consequently, human development itself.

The result of this is what can be understood as techno-banking education (Ubal et al, 2023). This concept is inspired by Paulo Freire's concept of banking education (1994; 1996)¹¹. Mediated by technology and artificial intelligence applications, education in the digital age of artificial intelligence becomes technobanking education because it treats the student only as a receiver, a watertight repository of knowledge that is transmitted to them. It is as if the student outsources their own thinking and their way of asserting themselves to the world to technology. The effect of this will be to limit the development of thought and deepen a single, uncritical, undiverse way of thinking, based on a model of simple, shallow, fragmented skills that impoverishes education and confiscates the creative capacity of individuals.

This reaffirms the issue that, with artificial intelligence devices, technology takes on a specifically human role, interfering in the way individuals deal with their problems. It is a situation of reversal in which applications guide, conduct, and order human life, removing its consciousness and autonomy: "with generative artificial intelligences by

¹¹ Much more than a method, the banking model of education criticized by Paulo Freire (1994; 1996) is a vision of the student and the teaching and learning process. It contemplates a situation in which the student is an inoperative part of the process, a passive being on whom the teacher deposits the knowledge he or she deems necessary, without caring whether or not this knowledge makes sense for the reality in which each student is inserted. In this case, education is merely the deposit of information, which does not produce dialogue, debate, emancipation, or autonomy. It is the education of repetition of what is already ready and does not always meet the demands that are presented in each specific situation.

For the first time, we have devices with virtually universal access capable of synthesizing and processing information, a capacity that was previously exclusive to human beings” (UBAL et al, 2023, p. 50). In this case, it is important to emphasize that technologies are not natural, but rather part of a process that can be positive or negative.

In this context, what Porto Júnior and San Segundo (2023) call a naturalized view of technology prevails, separated from the phenomenon of class struggle. This view denies that technology, which is part of human culture, is developed from the material basis of labor, omitting that the choices that are culturally made by individuals stem from a political dimension. The effect of this is that by naturalizing and fetishizing technology, a process of dehumanization occurs. The concept of technology fetishism is used here to

show that technology, which is presented to us as politically neutral, eternal, ahistorical, subject to strictly technical values and, therefore, not permeated by class struggle, is a historical and social construct. And, like merchandise, it tends to obscure class relations by diluting them in the seemingly non-specific content of technology (NOVAES, 2007, p. 75–76).

Although the appeal for the widespread use of artificial intelligence applications and resources in education is to generate greater autonomy and versatility for students, who take center stage in the process, what we see is the opposite. In this model, the focus is on competence and bureaucracy, combined with both the creation of a business opportunity and a strategy for the development of a single way of thinking. The student here is merely a secondary player who is operated by the technological apparatus that is increasingly concerned with forming individuals compatible with the demands of capital accumulation. Instead of working toward the integral development of critical individuals, capable of exercising political, social, and economic citizenship, the focus is solely on creating consumers of content in the face of on-demand, platform-based, and immediate education.

The discourse that the student is the protagonist and will learn what they want, when they want, and how they want is a trap that further deepens educational inequality, as it fragments and impoverishes the relationship between teaching and

¹² A naturalized view of technology is understood as a perspective in which it is considered neutral, autonomous, and deterministic, incapable of restraint or impossible to resist.

learning. It is believed that students are unable to make such choices and that, because of this, teachers—professionals trained and qualified to teach—should do so. The risk here is that more complex and difficult subjects will be neglected in favor of a series of simpler and more superficial topics¹³.

What we see here is the concealment of content as the center of the teaching and learning process, a de-schooling of the educational institution, through a poorly executed synthesis between a misinterpreted school reform and an impoverished technicality, implemented under the fallacy of scientific neutrality, rationality, modernization, efficiency, and productivity. It is important to note that attributing non-school problems to schools implies two problems. The first is the aforementioned emptying of the school of the functions for which it is qualified to perform. The second is a consequence of this, namely: the failure to solve these problems, since schools will have very little chance of resolving something that is outside their remit. This movement amplifies the notion of a crisis in education, within which any mediocre solution can be presented as a way out of what is not working.

The result of this has been the depletion of disciplinary content and knowledge construction among the lower classes, as well as a focus on organization and methods created by specialists outside the field of education. We therefore agree with Saviani when he states that

Content is fundamental, and without relevant, meaningful content, learning ceases to exist; it becomes a mockery, a farce. (...) Why is this content a priority? Precisely because mastery of culture is an indispensable tool for the political participation of the masses. If members of the lower classes do not master cultural content, they cannot assert their interests, because they are defenseless against the rulers, who use precisely this cultural content to legitimize and consolidate their domination. I sometimes put it this way: the dominated cannot liberate themselves unless they master what the dominant master. So, mastering what the

¹³ It is important to highlight that this movement has been intensifying since the counter-reform of secondary education. There have already been a number of complaints about the reduction of classical subjects in the school curriculum due to the arrival of a series of educational pathways and life projects, which deal with generalities, without any kind of academic or didactic rigor.

dominant subjects dominate is a condition of liberation (SAVIANI, 2021, p. 45).

Finally, it is worth noting that this entire ongoing process ultimately aims to exclude teachers from the teaching and learning process. This Netflixization of education, which, in order to be modern, must be on demand, works to do away with teachers, who are seen by large education companies as the main problem in education. Replacing teachers with artificial intelligence will make it easier to standardize the process and ensure the transmission of a single way of thinking to a group of individuals who will be unable to resist this movement. Not to mention that this will reduce costs, lessen the resistance of the teaching profession in the fight for their rights, and also make it impossible to broaden the horizons and demands of students.

Final thoughts

Based on Marx's reflections on the advancement of machinery and, consequently, technology, this reflection sought to show that every process of capital's advance over labor, knowledge, and education has direct and important repercussions in all dimensions of life. Without attributing a prophetic and fatalistic tone to Marx's text, it was possible to see that the discourse of productive and technological restructuring brought about by the idea of Industry 4.0 was already present in the reflections on machinery in *Capital*. Far from being a novelty and a sign of modernization, what we see is a phenomenon that recovers an old form of capital seeking various means to increase its value in an unlimited and exponential way. Although the current times are profoundly different from the context in which Marx's works were written, it must be recognized that the forms and strategies of capital—based on the exploitation of labor, the control of workers, the attack on rights, and the need to maintain inequality and misery—remain the same.

Although the starting point for the analysis carried out here developed from the productive restructuring brought about by Industry 4.0, this research goes further in attempting to understand the consequences of this phenomenon in the educational scenario, focusing its reflection on the effects that technological devices—

specifically artificial intelligence applications and Chat GPT – have on the teaching and learning relationship. Whether in industrial production or in the educational context, much more than the consolidation of educational technicality, what we observe is a movement that attempts to remove human beings from the process, who are increasingly being replaced by technological devices due to their inability to compete with the efficiency of technological devices and also due to economic issues. This confirms the statement by Araújo (2022) that, in the digital age, individuals produce their own obsolescence. However, this phenomenon is hardly evident to workers, due to the high degree of alienation that technology itself has caused.

The reflection developed here focused on the impacts that technology has on the relationship between language and thought. Considering that language is at the heart of the classroom structure (teaching and learning process), the new forms it takes in the face of new technologies operate both in the sense of erasing the teacher and students and in the sense of reconfiguring knowledge itself, reshaping the pedagogical triad (Houssaye, 1988). Teachers and students who use these new digital platforms outsource the development of their thinking to artificial intelligence, becoming hostages to a single, fragmented, shallow worldview committed to maintaining the *status quo*.

But, as Lenin (2020) would say, what is to be done? It is well known that in the neoliberal and digital landscape, the possibilities for resistance are drastically reduced, both because of isolation and intense competition between individuals and because of deepening alienation and lack of awareness about the phenomenon as such. The issue at hand must, first and foremost, be recognized as part of the class struggle. However, the solution should not be sought on the easy side. We must resist the temptation to take the shortcut of believing that technology is inherently bad. This would be close to a Luddite stance, whose thesis indicates the need to confront and destroy machines and any other technological instruments. Such a solution is neither reasonable nor feasible. Marx himself took the opposite position in his time when he stated that, rather than fighting against machinery, it is necessary to channel forces to fight and question the use that capital makes of technology. The author states that this is a strategy of capital that "imputes to its adversary the

foolishness of fighting not the capitalist use of machinery, but the machinery itself" (Marx, 2017, p. 514).

New technologies should not be demonized, but rather debated and reflected upon in terms of how they can be partners in furthering the development of human thought from the perspective of emancipation and autonomy. To this end, it is necessary to break the spell/fetish that reverses the natural order, whereby it is man who creates technology and not the other way around. In other words: it is the individual who needs to master the use of these instruments and not be dominated by them. In short, it is necessary to deconstruct deterministic conceptions, considering that technologies are socially constructed at the same time that societies are technological. The use of these new resources needs to be implemented in a way that generates greater autonomy, more free time, and greater emancipation, and not as instruments of control, surveillance, and intensification of working time.

Education can and should benefit from technology, but it should not do so from a commodification perspective. Hence, there is a renewed need to insist on an education system centered on building the knowledge necessary for human growth and development. To this end, another step will be essential, namely the democratization of the production and use of technologies so that they are accessible to all. Digital exclusion cannot be yet another path to segmentation and domination. In this case, we agree with Caldart (2023) when he states that "one of the characteristics of the formative intentionality of the school is pedagogical work with knowledge, aiming at an increasingly broad and deep understanding of reality" (Caldart, 2023, p. 245).

In this sense, it is necessary to emphasize that overcoming the problems of bourgeois education will not happen without overcoming the capitalist system and the bourgeois mode of production. We must not lose sight of the fact that the bourgeois school, even though it allows and organizes itself for the entry of all, will never be the same for everyone. Because of this, it is urgent to understand who benefits from and is interested in the discourse of technological restructuring promoted by industry and School 4.0. Does technology favor or hinder human emancipation? Do changes and advances in the technological and productive system serve to guarantee well-being and better living conditions for workers? Alongside this, it is central that in a country like Brazil, the

Brazil, where there is no significant production of the type of technology discussed here, the 4.0 proposal tends to further increase dependence on the central countries of capitalism. These and other issues indicate that the topic discussed here is broad, necessary, and urgent, and that this article has merely attempted to introduce the issue for debate, with the aim of signaling the need to identify threats and attacks in order to chart paths of resistance.

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